

Workshop at DH Benelux 2025: Contextualizing and Connecting Collections of Letters (CCCL)

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In this workshop, we explore the affordances developments in the field of digital humanities have established in relation to epistolary scholarship. In what ways can we enrich collections of letters to help guide researchers and a broader audience in the exploration and use of this particular type of historic data? We supply the workshop participants with use cases provided by previous and ongoing partner projects within the Huygens Institute to aid shared thinking, hands-on experience and dialogues on best practices.

We zoom in on the following three subtopics: i) current developments concerning the use of metadata and restricted vocabularies and ontologies; ii) desirable and attainable enrichments to contextualize collections of letters; iii) imaginable and beneficial crossovers between related but non-epistolary collections and the added value of establishing such broader context.

1 Scientific Scope and Relevant Projects

Epistolary research as any other domain in the digital humanities benefits from the usage of digital tools and technologies, as they open potential for broader scope investigations, connection of different resources and contextualisation at scale. Increasing the accessibility of letters in this way not only eventually serves the academic scholarship, but will also make letters as such more insightful for a general audience. The renewed national strategy of the Dutch Digital Heritage Network also highlights the connection of digital heritage as one of its basic principles, for example to support the (re)using of (digital) heritage (1).

The Huygens Institute, KNAW¹, having a long tradition of working with letter editions, currently leads the initiative to outline a roadmap for a *Brievenportaal* (centralised portal dedicated to letters) that will provide much needed possibilities for researchers to collect, process, and visualise this type of data across collections, see Section 1.1 for highlights of the technical aspects when working with letter collections and repositories as a whole. The numerous collections on Dutch history and culture that the Huygens Institute makes available online² have the potential to serve as such contextual material, and the definition of requirements from the users of the future *Brievenportaal* help to determine the ways the data will be formatted and presented, see Section 1.2 for details.

The proposed workshop follows the workshop 'Making scholarly collections of letters insightful and accessible for a wider audience' that was organized at DH Benelux 2024, continuing the discussion about access and use of data collections in the form of letters by the wider audience while delving deeper into several aspects of creating a letter portal and using hands-on cases.

1.1 Exploration of the Transition from Catalogus Epistularum Neerlandicarum (CEN) to the New Letters Portal - PICA Verkennen

The online Catalogus Epistularum Neerlandicarum (CEN)³ represents a letter database hosted by the National Library of the Netherlands (KB). It contains approximately 585,000 descriptions of individual letters and parts of correspondence written in the early-modern and modern period (ca. 1500 - present). The database contains information about more than two million letters. They come from the collections of Dutch heritage institutions, for example, the KB, the Museum of Literature (The Hague) and University libraries of Amsterdam (UvA, VU), Leiden, Groningen and Utrecht.

Originally, all partnering institutions have used the Gemeenschappelijk Geautomatiseerd Catalogiseersysteem (GGC)⁴ to catalogue their collections. However, the transition to work with the current state-of-the-art cataloguing standard, such as WorldCat⁵, by several institutions that are part of the UKB⁶, a partnership between 13 university libraries and the KB, has a number of implications for the existence of such a valuable digital humanities resource. On the content level, WorldCat cannot serve as a substitute for the CEN since it cannot distinguish individual letters in a collection, nor record essential correspondence metadata. Thus, such unbundling from GGC standard by KB and other organisations and the planned shut down of the current CEN in 2026 require a roadmap of alternative steps to avoid losing this valuable information.

The project 'PICA Verkennen' (PV) has two goals: to provide (1) an implementation plan and (2) a sustainability strategy for a national *Brievenportaal* that would replace the CEN. When implemented this replacement should result in a better accessible, cleaner, more user friendly, easier to update, more affordably sustainable and data-rich facility, serving a far wider community than the participating heritage institutions

¹ KNAW stands for the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen [Royal Dutch Academy of Arts and Sciences]

² <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/en/resources/>

³ <https://www.kb.nl/bron/catalogus-epistularum-neerlandicarum-cen>

⁴ <https://www.oclc.org/nl/ggc.html>

⁵ <https://worldcat.org>

⁶ <https://ukb.nl>

themselves. Thus, PV aims to explore ('verkennen') what a new CEN could look like. The vision of such a new letter portal was presented at the workshop focusing on the ways to harvest metadata from various cataloguing systems at different types of institutions (university libraries, state archives, museum libraries), and to enrich the data on different levels and at different steps of processing.

1.2 Contextualisation of the Resources for a Wider Audience - Werk aan Uitvoering (WaU)

The implementation of the Dutch government-wide program Werk aan Uitvoering (WaU) at the Huygens Institute⁷ has a goal to facilitate a variety of transition tracks that can lay the foundations for a comprehensive, open corpus of texts and data that can be explored in context, and that would be eventually accessible for the wider audience. Organisation of this workshop allows the project to showcase the recent achievements and developments at the institute, and to carry out consultations with the conference participants in order to align the way one uses state-of-the-art technologies to enrich metadata on a large scale and to explore potential for further collaborations on the use case of the letters portal.

2 State-of-the-art Projects and Initiatives as Building Blocks for Workshop Discussion

2.1 Letter Repositories

The idea of a portal dedicated to letters is not a novelty. Currently, there are ample repositories of letters online.

Early Modern Letters Online (EMLO),⁸ is a resource created by the Bodleian Library in collaboration with the Humanities Division of the University of Oxford. This repository combines early modern correspondences and letters from many different archives worldwide, where every letter is catalogued into EMLO with a mandatory set of metadata, and where available, a scan of the letter.

CEN database presents the metadata of the early-modern and modern letters, without additional material such as scans with quite basic functionality.

The Finnish LetterSampo⁹ is a database that is created not only to search for historical letters, but also to visualise and analyse the results by using the ready-to-use data analysis tools. The basic metadata stored in LetterSampo can be used to create network visualisations, such as a network of letters and a timeline of letters.

2.2 Data Enrichment

The data itself can serve as the source for its metadata contextualisation, for example when the content it contains is processed, and the information is extracted in the form that can be further used in the format of metadata. Two large scale projects run at the Huygens Institute explore how natural language processing tools can support data enrichment (identify languages, dates, named entities (persons, geographical names,

⁷ <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/en/projecten/werk-aan-uitvoering-wau/>

⁸ <http://emlo.bodleian.ox.ac.uk>

⁹ <https://lettersampo.demo.seco.cs.aalto.fi/en/>

institutions, events)) - GLOBALISE¹⁰ , Republic¹¹.

2.3 Collections Crossovers

Once the epistolary collections are catalogued in a standard format and connected between themselves, it opens opportunities to look for possible crossovers with other collections, for example, on the basis of Linked Open Data (LOD) technology. As a medium, letters are an excellent vehicle to carry out this research and develop applications visualising it, since they can deal with any topic and are ubiquitous in many different societal and historic frameworks.

At the Huygens Institute two projects work with artist's letters: Vincent van Gogh (in collaboration with the Van Gogh Museum)¹² and Piet Mondrian (in collaboration with RKD)¹³. In both cases they are prepared for a digital edition in conjunction with project eDITem (a Digital Infrastructure for text edition Templates)¹⁴. eDITem aims to create an open source innovative, modular, and sustainable publishing environment for digital editions. In the coming period, the Van Gogh letters and the Mondrian Papers are to be developed and published as enriched editions within eDITem. LOD datasets have been and will be made available: persons and artworks mentioned in the letters are linked to metadata available at the Netherlands Institute for Art History (RKD)¹⁵ or at other recognized authoritative data hubs.

3 Practical details of the workshop

We plan a full-day workshop with the following schedule:

- Introduction of the day
- Keynote presentation 'From Carriage to Cloud – Letter (meta)data within the CLARIN infrastructure' by Dieter Uytvanck
- Discussion of PICA Verkennen report over *Brievenportaal*
- Three sessions with workshop participants dedicated to the following topics and organised in the format 'presentation – hands-on use case – discussion'
 - Metadata and Vocabularie
 - * Presentations on collections descriptions:
 - Metadata of the Meertens Institute Collections by Judith Brouwer
 - Data-envelopes by Mari Wigham
 - * Hands-on use case: Data-envelopes in practice. How do you store the context of the dataset creation in machine readable form.
 - * Discussion
 - Data enrichment within letters - contextualizing entities, providing glossaries and the like

¹⁰ <https://globalise.huygens.knaw.nl>

¹¹ <https://goetgevonden.nl/project/>

¹² <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/en/resources/vincent-van-gogh-the-letters-2/>

¹³ <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/en/projecten/mondrian-edit-project/>

¹⁴ <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/en/projecten/editem/>

¹⁵ <https://www.rkd.nl/en>

- * Presentation by Nina Lamal about Suriano letters
- * Hands-on use case: Annotation of entities in letters in Transkribus and other tools
- * Discussion
- Presentation The Correspondence of the States General (1576-1796) – Linking Resolutions to Letters by Marijn Koolen
- Data collections crossovers
 - * Presentation Examples of artist letter projects by Juliette Huijgen
 - * Hands-on session: Creative pitch collection crossovers
 - * Discussion
- Wrap up discussion lead by Maria Eskevich

References

- [1] Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed and Cultuur en Wetenschap ministerie van Onderwijs. Nationale strategie digitaal erfgoed, November 2024.